

TECHNICAL REPORT

D1.2: Report 2 on actions to create interdisciplinary community around targeted drug delivery

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DELIVERABLE FACTSHEET

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Editor(s)	Maria Vliora (DF)
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Approved by	All project partners
Keywords	Interdisciplinary; working; groups.

Abstract	This deliverable report provides an update on the plan and actions for the creation of ANGIE's Interdisciplinary Working Groups (education, gender, long-term implications, potential future returns). The Interdisciplinary Working Groups aim to bring together different partners/stakeholders from different disciplines to explore different issues around targeted drug delivery in clinical environments.
Keywords	Interdisciplinary; working; groups.

HISTORY OF CHANGES

Version	Date	Creation / Change	Page
1.0	22/12/2022	Document approved by all Partners	All

PROJECT CONSORTIUM

Participant No.	Participant organisation name	Short name	Country
1. (Coordinator)	Swiss Federal Institute of Technology Zürich	ETH	Switzerland
2.	University of Würzburg	UoW	Germany
3.	University of Barcelona	UoB	Spain
4.	University of Crete	UoC	Greece
5.	Stroke Alliance for Europe (SAFE)	SAFE	Pan-European
6.	Experian	EXP	Portugal
7.	Magnebotix	MGBX	Switzerland
8.	Discovery Foundation	DF	Greece
9.	Verhaert	VERT	Belgium

1. INTRODUCTION

This deliverable document's activities that are performed in Work Package (WP) 1 "Build-up an interdisciplinary community around targeted drug delivery in clinical environment regarding education, gender differences, long-term implications, and potential future returns in societal/economic innovation and market creation". The WP1 objectives include:

- Creating ANGIE's Interdisciplinary Working Groups.
- Organising public debates.
- Targeting European and Local Governments.

The purpose of this document is to provide an update on the plan and actions for the creation of ANGIE's Interdisciplinary Working Groups (education, gender, long-term implications, potential future returns). The Interdisciplinary Working Groups aim to bring together different partners/stakeholders from different disciplines to explore different issues around targeted drug delivery in clinical environments.

1.1. Scope

The present document is the Deliverable 1.2 "D1.2: Report 2 on actions to create interdisciplinary community around targeted drug delivery" (henceforth referred to as D1.1.) of the ANGIE project. The main objective of D1.2 is to provide the plan for creating ANGIE's Interdisciplinary Working Groups. The ANGIE project aims to build-up an interdisciplinary community considering aspects of targeted drug delivery in clinical environments addressing:

- education
- gender differences
- long-term implications
- potential future returns in societal/economic innovation and market creation

1.2. Audience

This document (D1.2) is available to the public and the European Commission.

2. INTERDISCIPLINARY WORKING GROUPS

The purpose of the creation of ANGIE's Interdisciplinary Working Groups is to bring together stakeholders such as policy makers, the private sector, institutes, and civil society organisations to develop a new drug delivery technology, while promoting the public engagement, the ethical and legal discussions, as well as the relevant policy debates to foster its take-up by society.

The project partner responsible for the formation of the groups and the organisation of the meetings is Discovery Foundation (henceforth referred to as DF). The Dissemination and Innovation Manager had a meeting (via skype) with the Project Coordinator and the Technical Manager to discuss the following agenda:

1. Working group formation and assigning members
2. Writing a book on "Emerging Issues on Targeted Drug Delivery in Clinical Environments"
3. ANGIE Meeting on "Emerging Issues on Targeted Drug Delivery "
4. Chat Lab
5. ANGIE Podcast`

The details and decisions taken concerning the individual points listed above can be found below.

2.1. Working Group Formation and assigning members

The project partner DF sent invitations to all partners to participate in the groups and to nominate members for each group from within or outside their organisations.

After approaching several experts from within the consortium and external experts from Universities and Institutes from inside or out of Europe with extensive background regarding targeted drug delivery in the fields of

- education
- gender differences
- long-term implications
- potential future returns in societal/economic innovation and market creation,

four working groups have been created with focus on:

- Bioethics, education, and social implications
- Economics and long-term implications
- Health technology assessment and
- Ecosystems and innovation.

The interdisciplinary panel of external experts that constitute the Working groups can be seen in the following table:

Working Group	Full name	Expertise	Institution
Bioethics, education, and social implications			
	Dr. Alice Binazzi	Social marginality, deviance, and social disadvantage	University of Florence
	Prof. Ion Copoeru	Bioethics	Babes-Bolyai University
	Prof. Maria Rita Mancaniello	Social marginality, deviance, and social disadvantage	University of Florence
	Ms. Andreea Someșan	Bioethics	Babes-Bolyai University
Economics and long-term implications			
	Dr. Marino Bonaiuto	Technology acceptability	Sapienza University
	Prof. Manuela Joore	Health economic evaluation	Maastricht University
	Prof. Stefan Mühlebach	Education on nano-pharmaceuticals	University of Basel
	Dr. Camillo Porcaro	stroke rehabilitation	University of Padova
Health technology assessment			
	Dr. Antonio Cerasa	Health technology assessment in stroke	St Anna Institute, Crotona
	Dr. Sabine Grimm	Health technology assessment	Maastricht University
	Dr. Gennaro Tartarisco	Health technology assessment in stroke	Institute of Applied Sciences and Intelligent Systems of National Research Council of Italy.
	Prof. Maria Blanco-Prieto	Health technology assessment	University of Navara

Ecosystems and innovation			
	Romina Fucà	ecosystems and innovation	University of Verona
	João Leitão	ecosystems and innovation	University of Beira Interior
	Dina Pereira	ecosystems and innovation	University of Beira Interior
	Ernesto D.R. Santibañez Gonzalez	ecosystems and innovation	University of Talca, Chile

After one-on-one consultations with the external experts participating in the Working Groups and members of the Consortium it was decided that **a book with title “Emerging Issues on Targeted Drug Delivery in Clinical Environments”** will be written. The details for the proposed book can be found in the next section.

2.2. Writing book on “Emerging Issues on Targeted Drug Delivery”

After agreeing with the participants of the Working groups to author this book, we searched for publishing houses that could publish the proposed book. Thus, **Elsevier** was chosen as one of the most recognised publishing houses for scientific books. A book proposal was formatted and submitted through the proposal mailbox of Elsevier. The detailed book proposal can be found below:

Elsevier S&T Books • Book proposal form

Working title

Titles and subtitles should be focused to include key terms that readers would use if searching for information on this topic.

Emerging Issues on Targeted Drug Delivery in Clinical Environments

Author/editor information

Please list all authors or editors, including contact details, qualifications and experience, and outline why you are the right individual or team to prepare this book (short biography)

This book will be co-edited by Professor Aristides Tsatsakis and Dr Maria Vliora.

Aristides Tsatsakis is the Director of the Department of Toxicology and Forensic Sciences and Professor of Toxicology in Medical School at the University of Crete, Greece. In 2016 he was elected Foreign Member of the National Academy of Sciences of Russia (FMRAS), in 2017 Foreign Member of Fellow Academy of Toxicological Sciences (FATS, USA) and in 2018 Full Member of the World Academy of Sciences (FMWAS). In 2017, Prof. Aristides Tsatsakis was elected Honorary Member of Bulgarian Toxicology Society, in 2018 Honorary President of the European Institute of Nutritional Medicine (E.I.Nu.M.) and Honorary Member of EUROTOX and in 2019 Honorary Member of Slovak Society of Toxicology (SETOX).

Dr. Vliora Maria is a Molecular Biologist with extensive background in molecular biology and integrative physiology and she has previously worked on the development of biocompatible/biodegradable bioscaffolds for targeting adipose tissue. She has also worked on potential treatments in brain tumors as well as blood malignancies. She now works as a Project Manager in EU funded projects.

Background and purpose

Please 'set the scene'. What is your purpose in writing this book? Why is now the right time to publish it? What has changed in the market or the technology/subject recently? Include any background that helps to explain why there is a need for a new resource in this area.

Please provide a statement to answer the question: **what problem does this book solve?**

Navigating inside the body to treat injured tissues has fascinated people for centuries, but the required technologies have lagged far behind. The currently developing technology focuses on a future where health conditions will be treated from the inside, without opening up the body. Once the technology around targeted drug delivery is developed, the pharmaceutical industry will design new drugs to act only on the diseased cells, since we will be able to identify them from the inside. Medical schools will train physicians to use this new way of practicing medicine and the health systems will embrace the new technology for the benefit of the provided health care and the sustainability of the health systems.

Since targeted drug delivery is becoming a much closer reality in the clinical environments, it is time to start discussing all the emerging issues that will arise considering on how to handle the new information. Thus,

this book will be an excellent guide to answer the critical and philosophical questions that will occur around drug delivery systems and their application.

What problem does this book solve?

Many issues emerge in terms of social justice, privacy, confidentiality, long-term risks versus benefits, human enhancement, etc. As the technology advances further and intercepts other areas of biomedical research, additional issues and dilemmas will arise in terms of genomics, personalized medicine, bioinformatics, and neurobiology. These are tough, pressing issues that must be explored. In this book experts on the abovementioned issues will discuss and propose approaches towards solving these emerging problems

Target audience

Please describe your intended audience in as much detail as possible, e.g. industry sector, job role, level, subject specialism.

If the book could be used for a course please provide details, including program and level.

This book is targeting the scientific community, students at all levels of education, entrepreneurs in the field of drug delivery systems as well as entities opting to create legislation considering the emerging technologies

Benefits to audience & key features

With reference to the target audience(s) listed above, please give details of:

- The information needs and daily challenges of the audience relating to the subject that your book will address.
- The top 3 features and content in your book that will be most valuable to the reader.

Concise and updated presentations of topics such as equity in receiving treatment with targeted drug delivery systems, market identification for the application of drug delivery systems, bioethical issues that may arise with the release of the new technologies, discussion on potential long-term benefits/risks, or new insights in education around targeted drug delivery.

These subjects currently are not discussed in any other published books thus, they will benefit both the scientific community as well as entities related to creating legislation about the use of the new technology by presenting updated topics on targeted drug delivery.

The book will be valuable to the readers since:

- It will be discussing a wide array of topics around targeted drug delivery,
- The language that will be used is going to appeal to people from diverse backgrounds,
- The authors are experts on the discussed topics thus, the subject of each chapter will be discussed in a critical manner.

Competition

Please list the books that would compete most closely with your book and briefly describe how they compare. Why would readers choose your book over the competition?

- Targeted Drug Delivery: Concepts and Design, edited by Padma V. Devarajan and Sanyong Jain, 2014, Springer
- Drug Delivery with Targeted Nanoparticles: In Vitro and In Vivo Evaluation Methods, Edited By Yilmaz Capan, Adem Sahin, Hayrettin Tonbul, 2021, Jenny Stanford Publishing.

The books above cover a wide range of technical applications of drug delivery systems in several types of diseases and describe principles of the applied technological advances. They vaguely approach some ethical issues, but they do not expand or discuss them.

Our proposed book aims to answer all the emerging questions around the developing technology of targeted drug delivery, how it will be perceived by the research community, the health systems and students or specializing doctors. Also, how the developing technology will be incorporated in the market, how the production should run on ethical and environmentally friendly terms and finally it will answer to many bioethical issues that may arise.

Table of contents

Please provide here the planned content of your book, including chapter titles and a short paragraph or bullet points on the scope/initial content plan for each chapter (max 100 words). Please note that the Table of Contents can be provided in a separate Word document.

- All titles and subtitles should be focused to include key terms that readers would use if searching for information on this topic (e.g. 'Introduction to Renewable Energy Integration' rather than 'Introduction').
- In the case of an edited book, please include the names and affiliations of confirmed or tentative chapter authors alongside the chapter they will contribute. Please briefly provide information on the process that you have used to identify authors, and how you will ensure a

coherence between the various chapters in relations to the topic of the book.

- In order to maximise global appeal, we require geographically diverse contributors representing the international research community for the subject of the work.

The chapters included in this book will focus on four main topics:

- Gender differences and bioethical issues around targeted drug delivery.
- Development of new educational strategies on targeted drug delivery.
- Long term implications
- Potential future returns in societal/economic innovation and market creation.

To ensure the integrity of the opinions expressed in each chapter we only contacted experts in the above-mentioned fields.

Below you can find the tentative list of authors as well as their affiliated organisations.

- Professor Ion Copoeru, Babes-Bolyai University, Romania
- Professor Maria Rita Mancaniello, University of Florence, Department of Education, Languages, Interculture, Literature and Psychology, Italy
- Professor Manuela Joore, Maastricht University, The Netherlands.
- Dr. Camillo Porcaro, Department of Neuroscience and Padova Neuroscience Center (PNC), University of Padova, Italy

- Professor Stefan Mühlebach, University of Basel, Switzerland.
- Professor João Leitão, University of Beira Interior, Portugal
- Dr. Romina Fucà, University of Verona, Italy.
- Professor Ernesto Del Rosario Santibañez Gonzalez, Universidad de Talca, Facultad de Ingeniería, Chile.
- Dr. Marino Bonaiuto, Sapienza University, Faculty of Medicine and Psychology, Italy.
- Dr. Antonio Cerasa, St Anna Institute, Crotone, Italy
- Dr. Gennaro Tartarisco, Institute of Applied Sciences and Intelligent Systems of National Research Council of Italy, Messina unit, Italy.

The list is tentative, as already mentioned, thus, more authors are expected to join the authoring team.

To maximise global appeal of the book we reached experts from around the world to contribute to this work.

Inclusion & Diversity

Elsevier is committed to publishing content that is culturally sensitive, inclusive, from a diverse authorship, and does not perpetuate systemic inequalities. Should your project move forward, you will be asked to follow our [D&I Author Guidelines](#). **Proposals should identify how diversity and inclusion is represented in content and authorship.**

While reaching the authors that can contribute to writing this book the only criterion that was employed was their scientific expertise on the fields that are presented in the proposed book. Consistent with the D&I Author Guidelines, no other criterion (such as gender, people of color, or socially disadvantaged populations) has been applied. This way we ensured that we will increase the representation of any potentially under-represented social group.

Specifications

Please consider and let us know:

- Do you have an estimated word count range for your manuscript? Indicate if you are using [LaTeX](#). Ideal word count should be approximately 100,000.
- Please provide an estimated breakdown of the following types of visuals:
 - Line drawings/graphs:
 - Tables:

An approximate number of 250 pages is anticipated for this book, thus the word count should be around 100,000 words

- Data sets:
- Photos:
- Equations:

Are the visuals in black and white or require color?

- What stage is the manuscript at – no draft, some chapters are drafted, nearly complete, etc.
- **When can you deliver the final manuscript?** Please be realistic so that we can plan production and publication schedules accordingly.
- Any ancillary materials you anticipate providing alongside the book, [e.g.](#) downloadable code, video clips, etc.

Each chapter in the book is anticipated to have between 2 and 4 figures (corresponding either to graphs, tables, or photos. This includes any graphical abstracts that may be added in the start of some of the chapters.) the visuals should be in [colour](#).

As of today, we do not have a draft of the book but a brief outline of the sections/chapters that will be included. As mentioned above we anticipate to more authors than the ones referred in the tentative list above.

The manuscript is estimated to be delivered in December 2023.

Primary Use and Content types

Overall, would you consider your proposed content to be described as one of the following four primary uses. Please select one.

1. **Mostly research with up-and-coming practical applications included. Primary audience could include both researchers and practitioners/professionals such as engineers and applied scientists.**

Please mark with an X which of these content features would best suit this book, which you intend to include.

	Applying foundational knowledge to research, practice, or clinical setting
	Developing deeper understanding of one's field / core field
X	Staying current in one's field; keep abreast of hot topics/controversial issues
	Understanding new or adjacent fields
	Mastering new procedures/methodologies
X	Providing quick answers to key questions
	Reviewing primary literature
X	Bridging the gap between student and practice

Chapter Elements:

Please mark the content elements you plan to include in by placing an x in the left column next to each.

ELEMENTS	In every chapter (Y/N)	In selected chapters (Y/N)	How will you include this element? Is it clear in the table of contents? Please add detail here.

Definitions: What does this term mean?	N	Y	Wherever this applies there will be a distinct indication of the definition of the term that is explained
Foundational – Introductory: Intro to a subject the customer knows nothing about	Y	N	Every chapter will have an introduction so the reader can be introduced to the subject of the chapter.
Foundational – Advances: Expand knowledge on a subject the customer knows something about	Y	N	In all chapters we expect to contribute <u>in</u> the expansion of the knowledge of the audience on current issues of targeted drug delivery.
Methods/Research Methods: Explaining theory associated with an experiment	N	N	
Protocols: Step by step guide to show exactly how to reproduce an experiment	N	N	
Procedures/Processes: Step by step guide to show exactly how to reproduce a known procedure	N	N	
Applications/Case Studies: Examples of how a topic may be applied	Y	N	Examples of how the discussed topic should be applied in the future will be included in the chapters
Perspectives/Opinions: Providing different viewpoints on a subject	Y	N	In every chapter a substantial part of the discussed topic will be covered by the opinion of the expert/s authoring the section.
Reviews/Summaries/Review Articles: A summary of latest research or reviews of literature related to a particular concept/area of study	Y	N	The opinions discussed will be based on the existing literature so summaries of the available published information will also be included.
Latest Research/Recent Developments: Latest research/presentations, and/or journal articles related to a concept	Y	N	Wherever applicable the latest available information will be discussed
Reference Data/Properties: Providing data specific to work (i.e. Chemical reactivity, cooling properties, datasets)	Y	N	Wherever applicable the most updated data will be presented.
Analysis: Analytical tools to support the analysis of research results, data interpretation, and how to explain	N	N	
Calculations: Involves engineering, simulation modelling, analytical tools, and predictive modelling	N	N	
Future Implications: Big questions that are still out there	Y	Y	This book opts to answer emerging questions around targeted drug delivery and state future problems/questions/benefits that will occur in the field
Chapter/Learning Objectives: at the beginning of each chapter, required for content with predominant student audience	N	N	
Study Questions/Worked Problems: at the end of each <u>chapter</u> , <u>for</u> content with predominant student audience	N	N	

Enhancing discoverability

We are working towards providing users with consistent presentation, well-structured and highly discoverable content. There are a few ways to enhance this:

1. **Have each chapter follow the same structure or outline.** This is especially helpful in multi-contributed books since it brings more cohesion to the chapters. Can most of the chapters follow the same outline? If so, what would the outline include (e.g., Introduction, Principles, Methods, Current Applications, Future Predictions, Summary, References, etc.)?

The chapters will follow the same or similar outline depending on the discussed subject.

The outline will include, an introduction, data from the literature and discussion against targeted drug delivery,

2. Include visual elements that help with decision-making processes wherever possible – e.g. process diagrams, flowcharts, algorithms, etc. Can the book include these elements? If so, in which sections? Would visual abstracts be suitable for the book as a whole, and/or for some/all chapters of the book?

In the chapters that this applies we opt to add visual abstracts.

3. Ensure all figure captions are highly descriptive and understandable independent of the surrounding text so they can be indexed by search engines. For example, it's best to explicitly mention the type of illustration (e.g. line graph, photograph) and what it depicts, without referring back to the text (avoid e.g. "Detail of procedure listed above"). Can you ensure all figure captions will follow these guidelines?

All the figures that will be included will follow these guidelines.

4. Modularity. Chapters will be readable, discoverable and searchable independently of the main work on ScienceDirect, and this necessitates consideration of how they are presented and integrated. How will you ensure that individual chapters are prepared for potential use independently of the rest of the book?

The chapters will be prepared accordingly, so they can be used independently of the rest of the book.

5. Consider including video content that will give users a deeper understanding of your content, such as showing industrial facilities, laboratory setups, or preparation procedures. Videos are made available on ScienceDirect for all users but will not be visible in the printed book. Do you anticipate including videos with your manuscript? What will be the general content of the videos?

In this book we do not plan to include video content for the moment.

Energy with Purpose

Supporting the UN's SDGs and the commitments made in the Paris Agreement and more recently the Glasgow Climate Pact is a top priority for us. In September 2021, the Energy books team committed to only commissioning new content that supports the energy transition. Does this book support the Elsevier Energy Books team mission? If so, how? Which of the SDGs does this book support?

This book supports few of the UN's SDGs by promoting:

- Quality of education
- Gender equality
- Good Health and well being
- Decent work and economic growth
- Industry, Innovation, and infrastructure

This book will support the Elsevier Energy Books team mission by discussing topics such as the environmental benefits of using nanodevices for targeted drug delivery and how this will prevent future medical waste.

After proposing the book above a publisher from Elsevier house was assigned to us so we can continue developing the Table of Contents. Mr. Andre Wolff, manager of the Pharmacology and Pharmaceutical Science portfolios is now our contact for developing our book and since October 2022, we are in close collaboration to incorporate any comments and suggestions by the publisher. As can see above, in the book proposal that was submitted, there is a wide range of topics that will be discussed in the book, about the issues that are arising by the use of nanotechnology in targeted drug delivery.

To gather as much feedback and brainstorm in future meetings with the Working Groups, about the issues that may arise around targeted drug delivery, a public online event was organized in the frame of WP1. In the next section, detailed information about the organized meeting can be found.

2.3 ANGIE Meeting on “Emerging Issues on Targeted Drug Delivery “

An online **public event** was organised in the frame of WP1 titled “**Emerging Issues on Targeted Drug Delivery**”. The primary aim of this event was to get **feedback** from individuals out of the Consortium or the Working Groups on the issues they foresee arising by the eventual use of nanomedicine in Targeted Drug Delivery. Secondary aims were to **brainstorm** on the existing topics that have been suggested to be discussed in the proposed book and **suggest future activities** for the Working Groups.

The online event was organised for **the 28th November 2022 (16:00 CET)** and took place on Zoom. The event was announced on our Meetup group (<https://www.meetup.com/nanotechnology-for-targeted-drug-delivery-meetup-group/>).

The online event was also published on the social media of the ANGIE project (Twitter and Linked In) and an advertising campaign was also running on Linked In for a week before the event. The results of the advertising campaign can be seen below.

The **Linked In Campaign** ran from the 22nd to the 28th of November with ID number 216041433. It managed more than 46,000 impression and 110 clicks during this period. The event was set to be advertised in North and South America, Europe, and Asia with the intent to have the maximum reach to people and countries that are most involved in nanomedicine and targeted drug delivery (U.S., Japan, South Korea, U.K., and France). As this was an open event

Figure 1. Online event published on Meetup page of the ANGIE project

and was disseminated by the network of the ANGIE project, we made sure it reached stakeholders and members of the public in all possible countries. As can be seen in Figure 2 the post reached individuals working in **Education, Research, Health care services, Entrepreneurs, and people working in Business Developing.**

View: **Demographics** ▾ Display: **Job function** ▾ Columns: **Performance** ▾ Time range: **11/1/2022 - 11/30/2022** ▾

Attributes below reporting minimum will not be reported to protect **user privacy**.

Name ↕	Impressions ↕	Clicks ↕	Average CTR ↕
Education	23,394 (50.51%)	49 (44.95%)	0.21%
Research	11,345 (24.49%)	27 (24.77%)	0.24%
Healthcare Services	10,098 (21.8%)	28 (25.69%)	0.28%
Entrepreneurship	3,974 (8.58%)	11 (10.09%)	0.28%
Business Development	3,265 (7.05%)	8 (7.34%)	0.25%
Operations	3,085 (6.66%)	7 (6.42%)	0.23%

Figure 2. Performance of the Linked in campaign by job function, indicatively the 6 top categories are referred in the figure.

Campaign Name ↕	Impressions ↕	Clicks ↕	Average CTR ↕	Bid ↕	Average CPM ↕
1 campaign	46,319	109	0.24%	-	€12.95
Boost Post Website Visits_Nov 22, 2022 2, 13:28:17 ID: 216041433 - Sponsored Content	46,319	109	0.24%	Maximum Delivery	€12.95

Figure 3. Overall performance of Linked In campaign

The meeting was constituted by 2 sections. One section was the introductory presentation and **presentations from experts on Targeted Drug Delivery** from different scientific fields and the second was a **“Question and Answer” session** where everyone had the chance to ask questions to the speakers. The speakers were all members of the Consortium as well as member of the Working groups that were created.

Below you can find the **Meeting Agenda** as it was advertised as well as some “flyers” that were released considering the event:

Figure 4 Meeting Agenda and released flyers for "Emerging Issues on Targeted Drug Delivery" online event

Finally, the meeting was held on the 28th of November 2022 and was recorded. The presentations of the speakers as well as some the questions that took place before the Q&A session in the end will be soon uploaded on the ANGIE's channel on you tube (https://www.youtube.com/@angie_h2020).

The event was successful, with the participation of over 30 people out of the Consortium and a series of questions were asked in the following Q&A session.

**Nanorobots in drug delivery:
Sustainable supply chain issues**

Ernesto DR Santibanez Gonzalez, PhD
Nov, 2022

Logos: TALEA, ANIE, UNIFE

Project Overview – The Concept of ANGIE

Significance of strokes

- Second leading cause of death (WHO, Global health estimates, 2019)
- Third leading cause of disability (WHO, Global health estimates, 2019)
- Worldwide, every two seconds someone will have a stroke (UK Stroke Society, State of the Nation Report, 2019)
- One in six people will suffer a stroke in their lifetime (UK Stroke Society, State of the Nation Report, 2019)

What is a stroke?

A stroke is blockage in the brain vasculature, resulting in sudden cell death (CDC, 2019)

Ischemic Strokes are caused by a blood clot in the brain's arteries (NIH, Cardiovascular disease, 2008)

Ischemic strokes account for ~87% of all strokes (CDC, Cardiovascular disease, 2019)

Logos: ANIE, TALEA, UNIFE

Toxicity testing as a safety tool for Targeted Drug Delivery

ARISTIDIS M. TSATSAKIS
Professor of Toxicology, B.Sc., M.Sc., Ph.D., D.Sc., ERT

POLYCHRONIS D. STIVAKTAKIS
Senior Researcher, Toxicologist, Environmental Engineer, PhD, ERT

Logos: ANIE, TALEA, UNIFE, and institutional logos

Figure 5 Captions from the online event "Emerging Issues on Targeted Drug Delivery"

2.4 Chat Lab

In November 2022, Chat Lab was initiated on the webpage of ANGIE project (<https://h2020-angie.eu/chat-lab/>). Chat Lab is a platform for everyone. Through this platform we aim to initiate conversations between experts on issues related to Targeted Drug Delivery and people from the public or other experts, entrepreneurs, researchers, start ups etc. Participants of the Working Groups as well as members of the Consortium can interact with anyone that is interested either on the project itself or about Targeted Drug Delivery topics.

The user of the platform can choose any of the profiles that are available on the Chat Lab page according to the expertise of each Working Group member. Then on, an easy way to contact the expert has been inserted. An overview of the chat lab platform and the individual expert profiles can be seen below:

Chat Lab: meet the experts

Chat Lab is a place for everyone!

Here you will find experts from the ANGIE project as well as researchers and experts from all over the world, ready to answer all of your questions.

Click on the profile of the expert / researcher you would like to contact.

Dr. Polychronis Stivavtakis

Talk to me about toxicology, and toxic effects of nanodevices for targeted drug delivery on humans.

[CHAT WITH ME »](#)

Fabian Landers

Talk to me about small-scale robots, minimally invasive surgery, and the drug delivery platform that ANGIE strives to be.

[CHAT WITH ME »](#)

Ernesto D.R. Santibanez Gonzalez

Talk to me about manufacturing, supply chain, information technology, sustainability and business in relation to targeted drug delivery.

[CHAT WITH ME »](#)

Figure 6 The Chat Lab platform on the ANGIE website

Fabian was born and raised in the beautiful northern German city of Hamburg. Curious about the country of chocolate and mountains, he attended ETH Zurich, where he received his B.Sc. and M.Sc. in Mechanical engineering. During this time, he did a six-month internship at Evonik in the field of semiconductors in Hsinchu, Taiwan.

During his studies, he developed a keen interest in scaling phenomena and small-scale robots. For his Master's thesis, he joined the Harvard Micro-robotics Laboratory, where he developed electro-adhesive devices that enable small-scale robots to walk and climb on inclined and vertical surfaces.

Trading the Boston clam chowder for Swiss Raclette, he joined MSRL as a doctoral student in August 2019. His research puts a spotlight on the development, fabrication, and manipulation of small-scale robots for minimally invasive surgery and drug delivery. Within ANGIE, Fabian coordinates the development and manufacture of the drug delivery platform.

Chat with Fabian Landers

Your name

Your email

Subject

Your message (optional)

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Figure 7 Example of individual profiles of Chat Lab experts.

2.5 ANGIE Podcast

During the skype meeting of the Dissemination and Innovation Managers with the Coordinator and the Technical Manger of the Project the potential of raising awareness around the Emerging Issues on Targeted Drug Delivery in Clinical Environments was discussed.

It was decided that the ANGIE project will start its own podcast series that will be focused on different topics regarding Targeted Drug Delivery, other than the technical part of the project. This podcast series will be uploaded on the project's YouTube channel and will be available on the project's website. Each episode will be recorded edited (if needed) and released once every one or two moths depending on the availability of the interviewees.

The podcast will contain a series of Interviews with Researchers, experts in Targeted Drug Delivery, Entrepreneurs, Sociologists, Market Analysts, Medical experts, Educators etc. The interviewees will not necessarily be members of the Consortium or the Working Groups.

3. Future Actions

3.1. Working Group Meetings/ Book Development

The **Working Groups** will continue their meeting in the next year with focus on developing the book that was agreed to be published. As there is a lot of common ground on the topics that will be discussed in the books and as in the last event that was organised it was shown that all the future authors have valuable feedback to provide to each other, the Working Group meetings will not take place individually from now on. The participants will be invited in larger meetings where everyone will be able to discuss the topics of the chapters they will oversee.

We will also be in close contact with the assigned publisher Mr. Andre Wolff to keep on the right track while developing the book and find the appropriate peers to review our book in the end.

3.2. Other actions

The podcast series/ interviews will continue being recorded throughout the rest of the project period and be uploaded on the project's You Tube channel. It is planned to host experts on the field of Medical Education, Nanomedical advances, Consulting, Philosophy and Moral issues on the use of medical devices and members of the Consortium.

Moreover, more public events will be organized throughout the upcoming period on specific topics regarding Targeted Drug Delivery and its application in Clinical environments.